

“COMPUTERS & the INTERNET!”

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Annotation: The internet is defined as a global network of linked computers, servers, phones, and smart appliances that communicate with each other using the transmission control protocol (TCP) standard to enable the fast exchange of information and files, along with other types of services.

Key words: history of Internet, the structure of the computer, the place of the internet, modern computers

History of the Internet

- Mother of the Internet – ARPAnet (Advanced Research Projects Agency) developed by Department of Defense
- The Internet enables – Quick and easy communication via e-mail – International networking of computers
- Packet switching – The transfer of digital data via small packets – Allows multiple users to send and receive data simultaneously
- No centralized control – If one part of the Internet fails, other parts can still operate
- TCP/IP – Transmission Control Protocol/Internetworking Protocol
- Bandwidth – Information carrying capacity of communications lines
- The Internet enables – Quick and easy communication via e-mail – Remote login via telnet, bbs – File transfer via ftp – International networking of computers

What do we use Internet for?

- *to find and share information*
- *to google things for quick answers*
- *to study*
- *to listen to/download music and video*
- *to play online games*
- *to send and get emails*
- *to chat online*
- *to buy things online*
- *to work*
- *to plan and book trips*
- *to share your opinion*
- *to make money*

ENIAC and Earth Simulator

ENIAC電腦一景

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ENIAC (Electronic Numerical Integrator and Computer) 1946

Costs \$400,000

30 tons, 30-by-50-foot space

Can add 5000 numbers/sec or 14 10-digit multiplications/sec

Contains 17468 Tubes.

Earth Simulator (2002, Japan)

5,120 (640 8-way nodes) 500 MHz NEC CPUs

8 GFLOPS per CPU (41 TFLOPS total)

2 GB (4 512 MB FPLRAM modules) per CPU (10 TB total)

The web/ the net= the Internet (short ways, short forms) You can find that on the web or you can find it on the net.

- **Sign up**= to register
- **Sign in** =(every time you're going to the website you have to sign in, so means to enter your account)
- **Download**= take the information from the internet and put it on your computer)
- **Upload** = opposite, you take The information from your computer and you put it on to the Internet) for example you can upload photos if you have a facebook account.
- **Stream** – when you watch the movie online
- **User name**- a name used to indentify yourself
- **Log out** = when you finish using your account
- **Google** (n) (v)= look for the information on the website 'Google'
- 'Google it!'
- **Facebook** (n) (v)= to write some information in the Facebook

Computers, Information Technology, and You

- The Computer's Strengths
 - Speed
 - Accuracy
 - Consistency
 - Reliability
 - Communications
 - Memory Capability
- Comparing Computers and Humans
 - Human output is slower than computer output
 - Humans recognize patterns quicker than computers
 - Computers are 100% accurate in recalling stored information
 - Humans think, computers don't

1.2 What is a Computer?

- **Computer** – Device capable of performing computations and making logical decisions – Computers process data under the control of sets of instructions called computer programs
- **Hardware** – Various devices comprising a computer – Keyboard, screen, mouse, disks, memory, CD-ROM, and processing units

- **Software** – Programs that run on a computer (operation systems, application programs)
 - Structured programming, top-down stepwise refinement, functionalization, and object-oriented programming

THE INTERNET

1 Often, two or more computers are grouped and linked together *to make* sharing of files easier. **2** A file is a complete and separate unit (which/that contains) *containing* words, lists, photographs, videos, images, or audio materials (which/that are) created by the person (who use) *using* the computer. **3** *When* you group and link a number of computers, you form a network. **4** **Not only** files, **but also** all sorts of information can be exchanged *when* the network of computers are used *to exchange the saved* information. **5** Such information **either** can be saved *in* small microchips, (which/that are) smallest devices for data storage, **or** *in* other devices such as CDs, USBs, or floppy discs which are not in use for a long time.

6 *Although* USBs are fashionable, many people still use CDs *because* they are cheaper and easier *to send* by surface/regular mail. **7** However, it is still advised **that** *when* you receive an important file, you should store the file in more than one place (which/that includes) *including* e-mailing the file *to* your own e-mail adress! **8** Some people, *although not all*, save the print outs of *such* files. **9** Your database, which is all **the** information (which/that) you save, will look so big *if* you do so. **10** If you have a huge database, then, you should transfer or move some of the files to some other devices *such as* those (which/that are) mentioned above.

(1) In today's world, people use the Internet to communicate. In fact, many people use email which has replaced telephone and fax. Email is now extremely popular.

(2) We do not need to stay late to wait for a phone call because email allows for continuous communication.

(3) The emergence of the World Wide Web has helped the Internet become commonplace in offices and homes. Consumers can shop for goods via the Web from every sector, from books and CDs to cars and even houses. Banks use the Web to offer their clients instant account reports.

(4) In 1999, the U.S. Census Bureau collected information on e-commerce, which it defined as online sales. For the last three months of 1999, the bureau reported nearly \$5.2 billion in e-commerce sales (accounting for 0.63 percent of total sales), and nearly \$5.3 billion for the first quarter of 2000.

(5) More and more, people are going online to shop, learn about different products, search for jobs, manage finances, obtain health information and scan their hometown newspapers.

(6) The new Internet business continues to grow. Some experts estimate that almost all shopping will be done online in near future.

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